

Patient characteristics, conditions and visit data in a homœopathic family practice

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Purpose

Homœopathic practice by physicians is becoming more common in the US as well as in Europe, Latin America and parts of Asia. While studies have been done to document the efficacy of homœopathic medicines and treatment, no information exists about the characteristics of patients seeking homœopathic treatment, the conditions for which they seek care, or the number of visits and fees involved. As health care costs continue to increase, it becomes important to look at these factors in relation to non-conventional modes of treatment, as possible cost-cutting alternatives to standard medical care.

Materials and methods

Information about all patient visits in a two-physician homœopathic family practice was collected for the five-year period from January 1984 to December 1988. This information includes approximately 2,500 patients with 20,000 total office visits. Data will be analysed using the University of Washington IBM mainframe computer and the statistical program SAS. Data collected can be grouped into the following categories:

Demographic

Age
Sex

Diagnostic

Chief complaint (as reported by patient)
Diagnosis 1-5 (as reported by physician)
Type of visit (Acute or Chronic problem)

Visit data

Physician
Visit date
Visit number
Fee

Therapeutic

Medication given (homœopathic medicine)
Dosage of medicine (homœopathic potency)

Pharmacy (where medication purchased)
Other medicine/treatment prescribed

Efficacy

Analysis (curative, possible cure, incorrect, other)
Levels of health—better, worse, no change
 General
 Mental
 Emotional
 Physical
Homœopathic aggravation—yes or no
Other comments

Study design

The initial phase of data analysis will focus on the first three categories of information collected: demographic, diagnostic and visit data. These will be compared to results of the National Ambulatory Care Survey of family and general practitioners. Specific areas of data analysis include:

Demographic

Age, sex distribution by first visit
 all visits
 doctor
 each year

Diagnostic

Chief complaint (20 most common)
 All visits
 Sex and age distribution
 By doctor
 By year

Diagnosis 1

 All visits (20 most common, ICD-M codes)
 Sex and age distribution
 By doctor
 By year

Diagnostic categories (Diagnoses 1-5)

All visits

Sex and age distribution

By doctor

By year

Acute/chronic (type of visit)

As above

Visit data

Number of visits/year by age, sex, doctor, diagnosis categories

Return visit rate: # visits returning/# visits new pts. by age, sex, doctor, diagnostic categories

Visit # distribution by doctor and year: 1-10, 10-20, 20-30, 30-40, 40+

Follow up rate—# second visits/# first visits by doctor, age, sex

Duration of visit by diagnostic code, sex, age, visit number, doctor

Fees—Per visit, by age, sex, diagnostic code, doctor, visit number

Per year, by age, sex, diagnostic code, doctor